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Impact Factor: 3.43

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.376796

DOI URL: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.376796>

Cite this paper as : Irfanullah K , Zameer Q.A & Burney M.T (2016), Rebranding of News Channel Headlines Today to India Today: The impact of implementation of Non-linear News Philosophy, International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management , Vol.4,(Issue 5, Jul-2016), pp 01–10, DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.376796

REBRANDING OF NEWS CHANNEL HEADLINES TODAY TO INDIA TODAY: THE IMPACT OF IMPLEMENTATION OF NON- LINEAR NEWS PHILOSOPHY

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *The rebranding of Headlines Today, the English news channel from TV Today Network Ltd, to India Today, its 40-year-old flagship English news magazine was to keep pace and move to a world of seamless news on digital devices by adopting non-linear philosophy. The re-launch has given a new dimension of storytelling from shifting linear to being non linear as on the web. India Today can claim to be a new channel with fresh content. This rebranding has improved the credibility by aligning its idea of an integrated newsroom. This paper is focused to probe into (a) the viability of rebranding of Headlines Today in India Today (b) the role of established print brand of India Today in boosting the brand equity of digital India Today through rebranding (c) the viability of adopting non-linear news telling strategy to draw viewers.*

Design / Methodology/ Approach: *The study being exploratory in nature relies on secondary data collected from print and digital resources. One of the major tools that is applied in study of impact of television channel is Television Rating Point (TRP). The word TRP has now been reworded as TVT (Television Viewership in Thousands) and GRP (Gross Rating Point) is now GVT (Gross Viewership in Thousands). TRP is a tool provided to judge which programmes are viewed the most. This gives an index of the choice of the people and also the popularity of a particular channel.*

Findings: *TV journalism is linear. It has gone beyond that and brought India Today ethos of journalism on to television. India Today is a very big brand, and it exists across mediums. For people who are consuming news, dividing brand or mediums does not work. It is prudent*

to give brand that he trusts across platforms. With the new look, the channel has also narrow casted various segments of age groups. The group banded everything in Hindi under the name of Aaj Tak and everything in English under India Today. And that strategy has worked really well.

Limitations: Sources suggest that a huge number of channels in India use two spots on the cable network (dual frequency) and India Today TV were using dual frequency on multiple networks. However, this increased the chances of sampling and necessitates for re-sampling and retesting empirically on the basis of primary data.

Practical implications: Rebranding is not all about changing the logo but there is a broader idea upon which rebranding is pivoted on. It is an expensive process. If rebranding is done just for a tinkering of the logo, without actually reflecting what the audience wants to see, it will not work in the long run. Digitization has given viewers more choice to select what they want to pay for and watch. And with more progress on the digitization front, the future will see more and more TV channels rebranding.

Originality/Value: The paper assesses viewership of the English news genre which is so fragile that even minor changes look significant. Based on inputs from Broadcast Audience Research Council (BARC) and TAM Media Research Pvt. Ltd the trend has been tracked. It was also revealed that the effort of rebranding was paying off.

Key words: Non-linear news, Branding, Rebranding

1. INTRODUCTION

With rapid developments and changes in the audience behaviour, the need for rebranding and repositioning strategies of news channels arose widely to give a competitive edge. While rebranding, usually, the logo, color, and taglines are changed or improved, rebranding strategies are directly linked with brand equity management. The higher the brand equity or perceptive association, the more favorable will be the customer's response towards the promotional efforts of the brand. The rebranding of Headlines Today, the English news channel from TV Today Network Ltd, to India Today, its 40-year-old flagship English news magazine was to keep pace and move to a world of seamless news on digital devices by adopting non-linear philosophy. The re-launch has given a new dimension of storytelling from shifting linear to being non linear as on the web. News is now improved by making

shorter and tighter. Indeed, people prefer news in lists, quotes and bullets. India Today can claim to be a new channel with fresh content. This rebranding has improved the credibility by aligning its idea of an integrated newsroom. The decision to rebrand was a tool to differentiate itself from the pack. In this digital age, the viewer is overloaded with choices and information. Thereby, what a channel stands for is lost. Also, the trends keep changing, so what was relevant yesterday may not be relevant today. In the midst of all this clutter it is important to find relevance. It is important to keep up with the times. Not just for TV channels but for any brand. But it is not always about showing something new or taking up a new brand philosophy. Sometimes it is to bring a whole group under a bigger family, to consolidate a bouquet of channels. Rebranding is not all about changing the logo but there is a broader idea upon which rebranding is pivoted on. It is an expensive process. If rebranding is done just for a tinkering of the logo, without actually reflecting what the audience wants to see, it will not work in the long run. Digitization has given viewers more choice to select what they want to pay for and watch. And with more progress on the digitization front, the future will see more and more TV channels rebranding. The reasons for a revamp are often strong, driven by multiple factors, the strongest perhaps being to remain top of mind among viewers armed with a remote in their hands.

2. OBJECTIVES

This paper is focused to probe into (a) the viability of rebranding of Headlines Today in India Today (b) the role of established print brand of India Today in boosting the brand equity of digital India Today through rebranding (c) the viability of adopting non-linear news telling strategy to draw viewers.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Muzellec and Lambkin (2006) define rebranding as the creation of a new name, term, symbol or design for an established brand, in order to create a differentiation in the mind of stakeholders and competitors. Media industries have over the past few years embraced brand management (McDowell, 2006). The electronic media has advantage over print media due to the fact that print media is considered to be more of a 'habit' for the people. The electronic media is considered to be visually more appealing than print media and hence is perceived as more effective. This is not only true in terms that it conveys a message but also because it is a frequency medium, and hence is effective in registering it and likewise it also seem to

ensures high brand recall amongst viewers and potential customers (Upadhyay, 2014). In media, a print publication develops a readership that does not necessarily render into TV viewership of a TV channel. Brands in each segment are viewed separately (John, 2015). Media brands offer value propositions about what their customers can expect in terms of type of content, interactivity, and user experience. While traditional media, such as newspapers, sometimes are accused of being rigid and old fashioned, consumer studies show that many media brands, such as BBC, et al come across with associations such as —drive|| and —innovation|| (Grande, 2006). Likewise, studies of media-consumption experiences demonstrate a wide spectrum of emotions and associations that consumers attach to their household media (Calder & Malthouse, 2005). Riezebos (2002) describes the adoption of brand strategies as having two important motives. The first is a competitive motive in which a brand is used to enhance competitive advantage through emphasizing differentiation. A brand helps consumers understand and remember what distinguishes an offering from that of a competitor (Ries and Trout, 1997). Secondly, a brand strategy could, and should, add value to the product or service offering. From this perspective customers see more than the functional use of a product, and brands signal benefits on a multitude of dimensions based on the meanings and uses that customers associate with the brand (Levitt, 1980). Fredin (1997) conceptualized online news stories as being truly non-linear documents. Ketterer (2001) found that news consumers want more from their online publications than they can get from printed newspapers. His study found they drew significant value from being able to follow links in a news story according to their interest. Lowrey (2004) found that while linear story formats gave readers a greater sense of control of the story, they had no significant effect on the degree of perceived credibility, reader involvement or knowledge acquisition in relation to the same story presented in a non-linear format.

4. BACKGROUND

The rebranding of a news channel is not a new phenomenon. The major rebranding move of Ananda Bazar Patrika (ABP) News is a leading example. In March 2012 when Star's notice for pulling out of the joint venture finally came, the three big steps in the logistics of rebranding the entire network were put in place. Step one was the actual physical change. Everything from mike to vans, letterheads, employee and vendor contracts, etc was changed. Step two was to communicate the change to viewers, media buyers and advertisers, cable-operators and newsmakers. Step three was to keep the team steady. The whole name change

exercise is now a part of history. The consistency in delivering, better market share, confidence of advertisers, buyers, trade partners and newsmakers show rebranding of ABP was successful. The advantage in rebranding of Headlines Today into India Today was that the India Today was already a mega brand available in print, web and on the app. It was just another vehicle that helped the rebranding exercise faster. Headlines Today was launched with the idea of delivering fast snappy headline news. It was not a reporter-driven channel at all. The gravitas and authority of the India Today brand name was missing in Headlines Today. There was much endeavour to bring change by adding fresh weekend programming. The new-look channel also lent itself to innovative advertising options on the screen. It was opened to unobtrusive native advertising resulted in advertiser’s delight and welcomed by the editorial, which did not want ad breaks during breaking news. The leading factor in rebranding was based on the fact that viewer does not want linear news. The idea was to

bring non-linear web story by giving multi-dimensional storytelling on the story. The central theme was that a news channel needs to be a fact factory, which fitted with this philosophy. India Today Group is a well-known name and force to reckon with in the Indian media industry. The major rebranding exercise that India Today Group has gone through for its News Channel intrigues as to why did they just do that? Was this rebranding necessary? If yes, then what impact it would have on the broadcast genre and entire India Today Group? TV Today believes that this was not a rebranding exercise, but launch of a new 'news' channel, India Today Television . Some of the key people (anchors and

presenters) who were with the Headlines Today remain but the DNA of India Today Television was completely different from other news channels and the erstwhile Headlines Today. The new channel, given its brand, would live up to the reputation and DNA of India

Today, which is credible, influential and authoritative. This channel corroborates these values and brings to viewers the news done in the India Today way, which is well-researched, analytical, presented and across the spectrum (more than just politics). There would be a spectrum offering from politics, sports, art, cinema, trend, surveys, and others. The entire personality of the channel is extremely fluidic as we have put various elements which are leveraged to maximize impact and engagement.

5. METHODOLOGY

The study being exploratory in nature relies on secondary data. One of the major tools that are applied in study of impact of television channel is Television Rating Point (TRP). The word TRP has now been reworded as TVT (Television Viewership in Thousands) and GRP (Gross Rating Point) is now GVT (Gross Viewership in Thousands). TRP is a tool provided to judge which programmes are viewed the most. This gives an index of the choice of the people and also the popularity of a particular channel. For calculation purpose, a device is attached to the TV set in a few thousand viewers' houses for judging purpose. A channel's rating is a function of three things: reach, switching to the channel and the time spent on it. Switching to a particular channel is a function of brand pull. And the actual time spent on it depends on content. The content does play significant role in channel ranking. The opinion on the issue is divided. Some broadcasters believe that since almost all news channels follow the same stories all day without too much differentiation, news is terribly commoditized. In such a scenario, the channel with the distribution edge marches ahead. Content and branding both play an important role. Reach is just the number of people a channel is distributed to. Distribution is linear and directly proportionate to the amount of money spent. If one reaches more households more people will see the channel. So, some find India Today's excitement about occupying the lead slot based on one week's ratings a tad over-the-top. In fact, Times Now's viewers spent more time on the channel, driving up its relative share in English news. In any case, with its insignificant half a percent total share of television viewership, the English news genre is so fragile that even minor changes look significant. The India Today news channel was launched on 23 May 2015. The major outcome of the rebranding exercise was that India Today, formerly Headlines Today displaced market leader Times Now, from the Times Group under Times Global Broadcasting Co. Ltd.

The first is that there is not much of a difference between the measurement results of the Broadcast Audience Research Council (BARC) and its much maligned rival TAM Media Research Pvt. Ltd, although their numbers may not be the same, both ratings systems have thrown up similar trends. In the case of India Today, both television currencies showed an increased reach for the rebranded channel ahead of Times Now. BARC ratings of week 22 (2015) reveals that among English news channel in week 22, Times Now lost its leadership to India Today and was pushed back to the second slot with 264 TVTs. It seems the name change strategy has worked in favour of India Today (formerly Headlines Today) as the channel snatched the top spot with 354 TVTs and NDTV 24x7 at no. 3 scored 107 TVTs. The second major outcome is related to the importance of distribution in channel ranking, especially in the news genre. Broadcasters believe that if content is king, distribution is God. This had resulted India Today to march ahead of Times Now by focusing on expanding distribution reach. BARC, the joint industry body, launched its television audience measurement system. Its findings—whether in terms of channel rankings, reach or viewership surge have been similar to TAM. However, it is the matter of debate that the real picture could emerge once BARC expands its sample size. A handful of English news

channels and competitors to Headlines Today, including Times Now, CNN-IBN, NDTV 24X7, among others, pull in an estimated Rs. 400 crore in advertising. The company had started its advertising campaign. Ogilvy and Mather had created

Rank	Channel	Genre	Dual LCN networks	Cumulative reach (%)
1	India Today	English News	70	22
2	Den Snapdeal TV Shop	Teleshopping	62	11.1
3	MTV	Music	55	17.4
12	Times Now	English News	29	8.5
28	CNBC TV18	Business News	11	3.6

Source: Chrome Data Analytics and Media

the campaign for India Today. Living Media, the holding company of TV Today Network, holds 57% in the broadcaster. Focus on distribution led India Today surged ahead of Times Now by expanding distribution. Distribution expansion led to more sampling of the channel. The channel had opted for dual frequency in as many as 70 cable networks as opposed to 29 in the case of Times Now, which gave it an edge over the latter. Dual frequency means that the channel is available in two places on the same network. It took the leadership slot within two weeks of its launch and was ahead of Times Now in terms of sampling, both at the all-India level and in the six mega cities in Week 22. It had the maximum number of viewers in primetime in a specified target group. According to the data shared by BARC India (bestmediainfo.com, 2015) for English news genre for all India 1L+ households, Times Now led the pack with a gross rating of 355,000. CNN-IBN was the second most watched English

news channel with 263,000 gross rating. NDTV 24x7 stood third with a gross rating of 196,000. Considering 1 mn+ markets, as per the data shared by BARC subscribers, Times Now led the pack with 49 per cent relative share, followed by Headlines Today with 23 per cent and NDTV with 19 per cent relative share. In six metros, Times Now had a relative share of 51 per cent, followed by Headlines Today with 27 per cent and NDTV with 14 per cent relative share. Further slicing of the data gives the upper hand to Headlines Today as the channel was No. 1 in Mumbai + Delhi markets. Later, NewsX surged

ahead of competition in Week 47. The channel is number one in 6 Metros, with 116, while Times Now garners 112, NDTV 24x7 58, CNN-IBN 35 and Headlines Today gets 17 respectively. Source: TAM, CS M 25-44 AB YRS, Market: 6 Metros, day part: 0600 -2359 hrs, Week 47, GVTs (000). The ratings also reiterate that the channel had been dominating the English News space for more than 90 weeks in the target group of CS AB 25 -44 AB, Market 6 Metros, Daypart 0600-2359, Week 07‘ 13 to 44‘ 14 (tellytrp.in, 2014). India Today Television made a vigorous bid to overtake Times Now. It brought in Rajdeep Sardesai as consulting editor, re-branded itself and made aggressive changes in programming. The effort seems to be paying off; according to BARC, in the week 22 (May 24 to 31) India Today Television became Number 1 news channel. Its viewership touched 354 (000‘s sum), a metric used to assess a channels' reach, while Times Now, was pushed to the second slot with 264 (000‘s sum), triggering an all-out war (Ghosh, 2015).

6. REBRANDING AND NON-LINEAR NEWS PHILOSOPHY

A linear narrative starts at the beginning and reveals each detail as it each occurs in space and time. For example; A happened, then B, then C, and finally D. Nonlinear-narratives do not follow rules of space and time. They can start and end at anytime in the trajectory of the plotline. For example; C is described first, followed by A, B, and then D or D starts, followed by A, then jumps back to C, and ends with B. Nonlinear narratives often use flashbacks or flash forwards in which past or future events are revealed through memory or other methods during exposition of a current event. Headlines Today, which was launched in 2003 from the house of TV Today Network, has undergone a change. Apart from changing the name to India Today, it also donned new on-screen look. While introducing non-linear philosophy

in news, the channel did research with brand agency Chlorophyll and did eye movement study to find a way forward. They formed three separate teams who power the screen - each team responsible for one part of the screen. It needed internal team who understood content and technology. After an extensive research on how consumption of news has changed with coming in of smart phones, no primetime. Rebranding can happen in three ways: a refreshing of the on-air packaging, a proposition change or a change in content along with positioning. This last one is the only genuine rebranding process (Madhok, 2012). Usually graphics are modernised in order to keep up with rapid changes in the industry. This step may or may not be accompanied by a change in programming or positioning. A channel can also decide to adopt a specific, stated brand position or refresh the one they already have. This is known as a proposition change. A third way is to change the content in such a way that when people come to the channel, they can notice the change instantly. This is coupled with a change in positioning as well, so in most cases there will be an underlying theme in the content line-up. But there may be several reasons for rebranding of a news channel. Survey and research revealed that every other news channel had the same thing to say. A viewer in such a case would obviously get confused about which channel to choose. The pragmatic move supported by aggressive distribution expansion helped it land the leadership position in channel rankings in the English news genre. There are other factors also play a significant role such as carriage fee, etc. Even today, a national Hindi news channel pays as much as Rs.40-50 crore a year to cable operators to be seen across India. English news channels spend lower as they give the smaller towns a miss and concentrate their investment in large cities: they spend close to Rs.20-25 crore a year. For most news channels, lower carriage fee remains a pipe dream even after digitization has been rolled out: the fee, which declined 15-20% in the first phase of digitization, has been climbing as cable operators claim they need money to invest in digitizing their systems.

7. THE STRATEGY

The entire technological background of the new channel was completely different and it took around 8 months. Over the last year 2014, it had built the bench strength of the brand, and had brought in new programming and experts. It is believed at that point in time, it had got a good prime team of top-notch broadcast journalist and that adds to the gravitas of this. It was ready with it in February, but then it decided to time it along with BARC (Gupta, 2015).

Naming: Why did it choose the title name as India Today over Headlines Today? According to several consumer insights, it was found that the brand India Today was much ahead of brand Headlines Today in terms of respect and recall. It was an obvious thing especially with the legacy India Today had and it was felt that it was not leveraging its brand equity. Moving to Mediaplex, it was decided to build two brands, one for Hindi and another for English. On the digital side it was decided on aajtak.in and indiatoday.in. Now indiatoday.in has compressed all the digital aspects into it including magazine, television and videos, and in a period of 14-15 months it has gone in the top 3 news sites of India. Also the youth had embraced indiatoday.in which had demonstrated the kind of value that the brand brings to the table. Hence, it was synergized all its digital assets, and emphasized over to address the news television in a manner which is compelling and contemporary and with people consuming digital. The new channel had a very ‘app’ kind of a feel. As power amplification, India Today news channel and app, so this new channel would give a currency to the magazine. It would bring it back at the centre. So, it was thought that it would allow the magazine to do more and not leave it with the obligation to do certain things which it can leave. Together India Today brand has digital, TV and print, and all these mediums can work together. The TV was the missing link in the India Today’s portfolio, other than it had everything else to be a mega brand.

Choosing a fluidic screen: India Today Television screen shows multiple things at one time. It is similar to how mind multi-tasks. The screen is designed in an info-graphic manner to keep the viewer engaged via different themes and subjects such as news, features, sports and other things. The screen was designed after a lot of feedback, changing the way the story was told. It is believed that it does not tell the story linearly, and in the new design it shows many things as the interests of people are much wider. They are interested in doing multiple things together. Already they are looking at cluttered screens and looking at another screen. This is what is done by 22-45 TG (Target Group). Its screen is a far more alive because it is thought that time is a premium for its consumer. So they tried to give them as much as possible in one single screen. However the linearity was the prime objective because its TG is web and app savvy. The app language is not a single dish but a buffet. It does not have an interactive television but at least it can offer them different news. Till now, television provides basic news and rest by the second screen. It definitely cannot move away from the main news, but other info can be given as supplementary. It has thought differently and changed its workflows to do this. The entire idea is web because this is where the generation is going.

Narrowing the audience: The prominent question was that would this not take away the loyal audience who is outside this TG? They narrowed the audience. It was larger and bigger previously. The idea was that the bracket from 44-55 would adapt it but as a late adopters. Because the technology is so much in the forefront, 22-44 are leading the way. Now parents use the WhatsApp because their kids started using it. They may not adapt the screen initially but the strategists were sure that they will come on to the screen. It allows being far more social.

Re-orientation and Structural changes: The structural changes were insignificant. However, there were re-orientation through anchors and journalists, for the new format, which took around 3-4 months. The screen that it has created lends itself very beautifully to the new innovative ways of advertising. They wanted to enhance the viewer base and if they could improve the stickiness, it would have given a huge leg up in the ratings, views and automatically advertising also. As far as marketing for this campaign is concerned the brief was clear that India Today Television brand is here to usher in news that you get quickly and makes sense. So their tagline was ‘_Make Sense’. They worked with the brand consulting firm Chlorophyll and the creative agency is O&M. It is a three-month long multimedia campaign. The team discussed about the genre and how everybody outshouts the No.1 channel. The credibility of the genre was hit and their idea was how to restore it, how do they present the news in a format that makes sense in a manner, which is compelling and engaging. The brand like India Today made the difference. It boasts of a credible brand. The discussion was to become the one stop channel for the viewer. The agency loved the idea and said that this is what India Today stands for and they had to break through the clutter. That itself was the brief.

Advertising Rates: They hoped that with this their advertising rates also moved upwards because they expected viewership to move upward. They did not just looking at the market share but also at expanding the market. People who have moved away from genre and they hoped to engage them back.

Programming Changes: They attempted to bring back a lot of genres back to television, which are completely gone such as art, culture, books and others. They focused on technology and education. By juicing the content turbine which they had created in the years, it was hoped to achieve this endeavor. There is a lot of information that they created but were

not able to use and people love that. With more information on the screen, they aim to pass it to the viewer without being judgmental, so that people make a call.

New programmes: It included a travel show with celebrities on weekends, a show around Robb report, Luxury show, personal finance, and others. It produced simplified business programs for the people. They had partnered with Euro News for international bulletins, over the weekend including another marquee show with Chetan Bhagat. The target was to become the number one on its rules and not what others do. They did not want ‘copy-cat’ journalism.

8. CONCLUSION

As rebrandings go, this exercise is undoubtedly bold, running many risks. The obvious questions are: Is the brand strong enough to work magic in the visual and print media together? Can a print brand’s appeal be superimposed on a television network to get better TRPs? Will core readers of print magazine, the flagship 30-year-old magazine, switch to watching the electronic channel having fierce competitors? Marketing mandarins believed that a brand provides the pull and the marketing the push. In this case, there seems to be some confusion between the branding and marketing strategy. It is difficult to imagine viewers being won over with snappy headlines, which has been a long-running philosophy of the India Today group. A lot of viewers grew up in an age when there was only Doordarshan to watch. The number of shows was less and choices were limited. With the entry of cable television the viewers were suddenly spoilt for choice. Digitization has opened the door for hundreds of channels to make entry in living rooms. But with numbers come the struggle to survive. And one of the survival strategies which every channel has gone back to time and again has been to rediscover itself. So, every few years, we see channels rebranding themselves – mostly a new look and feel, a new positioning, and new colours and sometimes a new logo too. The rebranding of India Today was different as it brought change in the entire philosophy. TV journalism is linear. It has gone beyond that and brought India Today ethos of journalism on to television. India Today is a very big brand, and it exists across mediums. For people who are consuming news, dividing brand or mediums does not work. It is prudent to give brand that he trusts across platforms. With the new look, the channel has also narrow casted various segments of age groups. The group banded everything in Hindi under the name of Aaj Tak and everything in English under India Today. And that strategy has worked really well. So the question really here is what will India Today TV give what Headlines Today couldn’t? What does India Today stand for that Headlines Today didn’t? Rajdeep

Sardesai's stint as an anchor of a prime time show and Karan Thapar's show has given the channel some heft and viewership. But will this be enough? Already, the channel has plunged headlong into a battle for TRPs with Times Now. It claimed to have toppled Times Now (on the back of its coverage of the Lalit Modi story and interview), while its editor Rahul Kanwal accused Times Now of trying to reclaim the top spot by —hook or by crook. Ratings by different agencies differ and are based on different parameters. It is debatable whether the India Today print brand has grown additional sinews in the last decade to pass on excess pulling muscle to its TV network. The magazine and the group began to lose prominence in the last decade when the digital churn started. India Today tried several digital strategies, most of which didn't work too well. The main portal was once put behind a pay wall, then a website with —snappy headlines was launched, and then a commerce website only for invitees was set up – all with lukewarm success. Cross-connecting brand identities is a risky business. Times Now takes its brand equity from its print variant but that was no rebranding. Today, the channel and the newspaper travel different paths. Times Now today is a big brand in its own right and does not need rebranding as Times of India TV. Aaj Tak has done well without the India Today logo hanging anywhere near it. At the same time, some regional editions of India Today with the same branding have shut down, showing that in regional languages the brand pull doesn't work. So where does this brand equity work? In the case of the TV channel rebranding, many will argue that the magazine was the weaker brand among the two and actually the magazine should have been renamed as Headlines Today, with the bright future of TV and the dismal future of print in mind. Both the television channel and the magazine need to rejuvenate in the coming years. That anxiety has set in in the group is evidenced by the fact that India Today magazine has had four editors in the last two-three years. The TV rebranding too can be seen as part of this struggle to regain its pre-eminence. Within a week of losing leadership to India Today, Times Now was number one in the English news genre again (BARC). Both players adopted a strategy used ever since news channel took off in 2003 – of buying reach and attacking the other with selective data. It gave only short term result (Kohli-Khandekar, 2015).

9. DIRECTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

According to Chrome Data Analytics and Media, 150 of the 800-odd channels in India were using two spots on the cable network (dual frequency). Chrome Data has confirmed that India Today TV was using dual frequency on 70 cable networks (the highest by any channel) and

Times Now on 29 which increased the chances of sampling. This necessitates re-sampling and retesting empirically on the basis of primary data.

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